

A Better Approach to Requirement Engineering with Agile Process

Manasi U. Kulkarni, Nirmala Shinde, Pramila Chawan
 Department of Computer Technology,
 VJTI University, Mumbai
 manasi_v_d@rediffmail.com
 nirmala_baloorkar@rediffmail.com
 pmchawan@vjti.org.in

Abstract — Agile methodologies are gaining popularity quickly, receiving increasing support from the software development community. Current requirements engineering practices have addressed traceability approaches for well defined phase-driven development models. This article gives brief idea of traditional requirements engineering approaches and agile software development. It talks about numerous aspects of requirements engineering and their suitability for agile approaches. It gives a brief idea of benefits of requirements traceability – a key enabler for large-scale change management and its use in Agile Methods.

Keywords – Agile Process, Requirement Engineering, Traceability, JAD, ECHO

I. INTRODUCTION

Agile software development approaches have become more popular during the last few years. Several methods have been developed with the aim to be able to deliver software faster and to ensure that the software meets customer changing needs. According to a study of the Standish Group, five of the eight main factors for project failure deal with requirements:

Table I : Main causes of project failure

Problem	%
Incomplete requirements	13.1
Low customer involvement	12.4
Lack of resources	10.6
Unrealistic expectations	9.9
Lack of management support	9.3
Changes in the requirements	8.7
Lack of planning	8.1
Useless requirements	7.5

Engineering requirements for software systems has been perceived as one of the key steps in a successful software development endeavor.

II. REQUIREMENT ENGINEERING IN TRADITIONAL SOFTWARE ENGINEERING

Requirements engineering is concerned with identifying, modeling, communicating and documenting the requirements for a system, and the contexts in which the system will be used. The aim of RE is to help to know what to build before system development starts in order to prevent costly rework. The RE

process consists of five main activities: Elicitation, Analysis and negotiation, Documentation, Validation, and Management.

Steps in Requirement Engineering are as follows:

- Requirements Elicitation: It invokes the task to find out the requirements
- Requirements Analysis and Negotiation: It represents the problem domain which will be built
- Requirements Specification and Validation: It defines the right system and an essence of agreement between the users and developers.
- Requirements Management and Documentation: This ensures the software continues to meet the expectations of the users.

Fig. 1 : The steps in RE for *Waterfall model*

The main problem with the waterfall model is the inflexible division of a project into separate stages, so that commitments are made early on, and it is difficult to react to changes in requirements. Iterations are expensive. This means that the waterfall model is likely to be unsuitable if requirements are not well understood or are likely to change in the course of the project.

Fig. 2 : The steps in RE for *Iterative model*

Fig. 3: The steps in RE for Spiral model

Most agile methods share other iterative and incremental development methods, emphasis on building releasable software in short time periods. Agile development differs from other development models: in this model time periods are measured in weeks rather than months and work is performed in a highly collaborative manner. Most agile methods also differ by treating their time period as a strict time-box.

Agile methods produce completely developed and tested features every few weeks. The emphasis is on obtaining the smallest workable piece of functionality to deliver business value early, and continually improving it and adding further functionality throughout the life of the project.

Requirement Engineering is often heavily relying on documentation for knowledge sharing while agile methods are focusing on face-to-face collaboration between customers and developers to reach similar goals. Agile methods have emerged around improving customer satisfaction, adoption to changing requirements, frequently delivering working software, and close collaboration of business people and developers.

III. REQUIREMENT ENGINEERING IN AGILE METHODOLOGY

In comparison to traditional software processes, agile development is less document-centric and more code-oriented.

Two key differences between traditional and agile method are: Agile methods are adaptive rather than predictive and Agile methods are people-oriented rather than process-oriented.

Customer involvement is the key factor of the. A key point in all agile approaches is to have the customer 'accessible' or 'on-site'. Usually, the term "customer" identifies a set of stakeholders that belongs to the organization that is paying for the development of a software product.

This customer should be a domain expert and able to make important decisions such as accepting the product, prioritize requirements, etc. The customer should always be available to answer questions coming from the development team. He is able to answer all questions from developer. The customer is able to make final decisions and commitments. The agile methods involve the customer throughout the whole development process.

JAD (Joint Application Development) sessions are used in ASD (Adaptive Software Development) to increase customer involvement.

Interviews: As customer involvement is a primary goal of agile software development. Interviews provide direct and 'unfiltered' access to the needed knowledge.

Prioritization: A common practice is to implement the highest priority features first to deliver the most business value. During development, the understanding of the project increases and new requirements are added. To keep priorities up-to-date, prioritization is repeated frequently during the whole development process.

In Agile Modeling, models are used to communicate understanding of a small part of the system under development.

Requirements engineering in Agile Model focuses on:

1. Reduction of waste from requirements
2. Managing the requirements evolution

Agile Modeling adopts several techniques focused on the interaction between the customer and the development team:

- **Requirements elicitation** is an activity in which the whole development team is involved and the probability of misunderstandings decreases.
- Requirements are collected using the **informal language of the customer** so the developers must have knowledge of the domain of the customer in order to understand him.
- The **interaction** between the development team and the customer is maintained.
- **Requirements splitting:** If the development team considers a requirement too complex, this technique helps the customer to split it in simpler ones. This splitting helps developers to understand better the functionalities requested by the customer.

In order to reduce this kind of waste, Agile Modeling uses the following techniques:

- **Requirements prioritization:** the customer and the development team assign priorities to each requirement in order to identify more important features that have to be implemented first.
- **Incremental releases:** functionalities are released in small but frequent bunches (from 2 weeks to 2 months), in order to collect feedback from the customer.

After the identification of the functionalities to include into the system, the customer and the development team assign priorities to them. The prioritization activity is performed in four steps:

1. The development team estimates the time required to implement each functionality. If the effort required is too high, the requirement is split into simpler ones that can be implemented with less effort.
2. The customer specifies business priorities for each functionality.
3. According to the business priorities, the development team assigns a risk factor to the functionalities.
4. The customer and the development team identify the functionalities to implement in the iteration.

IV. REQUIREMENT EVOLUTION

Agile Model assumes that it is very hard to elicit all the requirements from the user upfront, at the beginning of a development project. Agile companies are aware that changes are inevitable and they include the management of variability into the development process. Agile Model bases the requirements collection and management on three main hypotheses.

- Requirements are not well known at the beginning of the project.
- Requirements change.
- Making changes is not expensive.

Therefore development phases are grouped together in very short iterations and binding decisions are taken as late as possible, the growing of the costs is limited.

The requirements are not specified in details at contract level but defined step by step during the project through a negotiation process between the customer and the development team. Managing variability is a challenge that Agile Model approach in two ways:

1. **Decoupling requirements:** requirements have to be as independent as possible in order to clearly identify what to implement and make the order of their implementation irrelevant.
2. **Requirement elicitation and prioritization:** at the beginning of every iteration, there is a requirements collection and prioritization activity. During that, new requirements are identified and prioritized.

Documentation In agile software development, creating complete and consistent requirements documents is seen as infeasible or, at least, as not cost effective. Some agile methods include a kind of documentation or recommend the use of a requirements document (DSDM, Scrum, Crystal) but the decision on its extend is left to the development team and not described in detail.

Validation Agile approaches use frequent review meetings and acceptance tests for requirements validation. Review meetings show that the project is in target and schedule increasing customer trust & confidence in the team or highlighting problems very early.

V. TOOLS FOR REQUIREMENTS MANAGEMENT IN AGILE METHODS

The most popular tools for requirements engineering in several AMs are paper, pencil, and a pin board. The general purpose tools there are:

- **UML modeling tools:** such tools are used in two ways: (1) to write a high level description of the application; (2) to reverse engineer the code to create documentation.
- **Requirements negotiation tools:** this kind of tools helps developers and customer to identify, prioritize, and manage requirements in different environments, including the Agile one.
- **Instant messaging tools:** these tools are useful to keep in touch with the customer in order to discuss requirements when he is not on-site.
- **Project management tools:** It is one of the ad-hoc applications, such tools focus on specific practices used in AMs and helps to store and retrieve requirements documents (e.g., user stories) in an electronic format.

VI. TRACEABILITY

Requirements traceability refers to the ability to describe and follow the life of a requirement, in both a forwards and backwards direction.

Maintaining traceability in the standard fashion would require manual tracking and maintenance from artifact to artifact, across the different stages. In complex projects, management of the links becomes burdensome, and accuracy depends on the frequency of updates. If not maintained correctly, links from one artifact to another may be incorrect, as requirements or other requirements documents are disposed of. The nature of agile development artifacts makes it difficult for static, document-centric models to fulfill these needs. Recording links between changing requirements and design constructs is only successful when there is a clear understanding of how changing customer needs are mapped onto requirements specifications. For traceability to succeed in agile development models, the relationship between conversations about the problem and refinement into requirements specifications must first be addressed.

Fig. 4 : Maintaining traceability manually in an agile project space.

VI-I A TOOL-BASED APPROACH FOR REQUIREMENTS TRACEABILITY

Echo is a tool-based approach designed to leverage the activities carried out by agile development teams to deliver the benefits of requirements engineering and traceability practices. Rather than requiring changes in development processes and practices, Echo takes advantage of the elaboration activities carried out when detailing user stories (or other agile requirements constructs) into other project artifacts (e.g. CRC, CAT, Plans, etc). The team, following agile best practices, is often engaged in the refinement, exploration, synthesis of the initial user story into a more precise set of specifications representing the customer needs and the solution to be developed. Echo, by providing a tool-based mechanism to facilitate such activities, enables the development team to progressively refine needs statements into solution requirements as the project carries on. More importantly, the

transposition of structure onto unstructured content, as a result of user-driven elaboration, enables the recording of software development artifacts like requirements specifications. Additionally, the set of relationships that document design rationale are also captured.

Echo accounts for the previously detailed constraints critical to agile development teams. It creates a conversation-centric model for recording exchanges with customers and team members. Echo allows users to progressively structure the content into specifications of the solution. In face-to-face analysis meetings, where discussions reach new insights, the discussion is captured and ultimately recorded as part of a specification. Echo also helps assess the impact of changes as the implicitly captured links allow forward and backward traceability between structured and unstructured content.

VII. CASE STUDY ON EXTREME PROGRAMMING (XP)

1. Gathering Stories and Conversations

As previously stated agile development practices prefer the use of informal methods to track and document requirements. Extreme Programming involves the user story best practice. Stories are short descriptions of features or behaviors of a system, written by the customer generally on index cards. Stories are the vehicles that then drive conversations, which uncover details about the story's described task, possibly including an in-depth description of the task, the risk, the cost, the priority, and outstanding technical or design issues. The actual information varies from project to project, and team to team, as the agile methodology stresses the importance of using practices that fit the team. Extreme Programming maintains that the knowledge generated from the story conversations should be recorded and acted out through CRC cards, which can then be attached to the story cards. In this fashion, story cards and attached documents become tokens of knowledge that may be physically carried around.

Fig. 5 : A sample information flow based on XP.

Agile practitioners express their preference for the simple tools currently in use: index cards, pushpins, and corkboards. Recently, varying results have been observed as more project of different size and complexity test the effectiveness of agile practices heavily reliant on analog artifacts. Such outcomes suggest that additional software-based tools could help overcome the natural limitations of the analog world if espousing the human-centric communication so centric to agile development practices.

2. Maintaining Traceability

As projects become larger and more complex, traceability becomes increasingly difficult to maintain. In small project using agile practices, the lack of documented traceability can be

overcome by asking other team members about a particular task, in essence, echoing the original conversation. The developers often used source code as their primary information source, as documentation was generally considered abstract and out of date. Even though stories are the first artifact created by XP projects, the stories are often the result of a problem statement, request for proposal, or a contract with the customer. Stories are then extracted from the document, and often times, after the review process, restructured to another form of requirements artifact. Access to documented traceability is indeed very valuable. However, the manual burden or that introduced by existing tools to track traceability directly contradicts with the principles of agile practices. Typically, tools require declaration of each artifact, its dependencies, and manual maintenance of links between artifacts. Managing change to maintain predictability and quality requires rigorous application of best-practices, such as just-in-time planning, traceability, and continuous requirements gathering and validation. Solutions for agile practices must closely mimic and support these human-centric practices and adopt the principles promoted by collaborative authoring where content progressively contributes structures like plans, stories, tasks and structures effortlessly trace to changing content.

Fig 6 : Traceability from code, to CRC, to story, overlooking conversation capture.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The Requirement Engineering process phases: elicitation, analysis, and validation are present in all agile processes. The techniques used vary in the different approaches and the phases are not as clearly separated as in the RE process - they merge in some ways. They are also repeated in each iteration - which makes it harder to distinguish between the phases.

The techniques used in the agile development processes are some times described vary vaguely and the actual implementation is left to the developers. This is a result of the emphasis on highly skilled people in agile methods: "good" developers will do the "right thing". In the spirit of agility, the focus on customer needs and software development is maintained during requirements elicitation activity.

This paper has given introduction to the Agile Methods and to their approaches to requirements elicitation and management. Traceability is beneficial to the software development process, but is difficult and complex to manage accurately. Echo delivers a transparent model in which traceability is implicitly become challenging when dealing with large scale or distributed software development efforts.

This paper presents the results from a study where a requirements management tool was developed to meet the needs of a fast moving XP project. The aim of the tool was to minimize rework

and to automate time consuming paper-pen practices, as well as to achieve accurate traceability.

IX. REFERENCES:

- [1] Christopher Lee : *An Agile Approach to Capturing Requirements and Traceability.*
- [2] Frauke P, Dr. Armin E, Dr. Frank : *Requirements Engineering and Agile Software Development , 2003 IEEE*
- [3] Alberto Sillitti, Giancarlo Succi : *Requirements Engineering for Agile Methods.*
- [4] Sujatha Bulandran : *Requirement Analysis, The University of Western Australia*
- [5] <http://www.agilemodeling.com/>
- [6] Armin Eberlein, Julio Cesar Sampaio do Prado Leite: *Agile Requirements Definition: A View from Requirements Engineering.*
- [7] M. A. Awad: *A Comparison between Agile and Traditional Software Development Methodologies .*